

**SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING THE VIRTUES
OF RESPONSIBILITY AND DEDICATION****Daliyeva Muattarkhon Mukhtorovna**Independent Researcher of Fergana state university,
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ABSTRACT

The article studies the theoretical foundations of the study of the interpretation of responsibility and self-sacrifice in the spiritual and moral heritage of the Uzbek people, the philosophical analysis of the interpretation of responsibility and self-sacrifice in the spiritual and moral heritage of the Uzbek people, the future tasks of developing responsibility and self-sacrifice in society based on the spiritual and moral heritage of the Uzbek people. Also, an analytical analysis of the qualities of ecological responsibility and self-sacrifice in the literary heritage of the Uzbek people is provided.

Introduction

In the present time, when serious threats to humanity are intensifying, fostering the sense of devotion (fidoiylilik) and explaining its significance as a high moral principle has become an urgent social task for scholars. Indeed, moral principles represent specific forms of moral consciousness in which ethical demands are expressed in a relatively general way. They manifest as requirements imposed by society on the individual, defining a person's moral essence, the meaning of life, and the fundamental aspects of interpersonal relations. Consequently, moral principles indicate the general direction of human behavior and serve as the basis for many moral norms.

Literature review and methods

The theoretical foundations for studying the interpretation of responsibility and devotion in the spiritual and moral heritage of nations, as well as the philosophical analysis of these concepts in the Uzbek spiritual and ethical legacy, and the issues of promoting responsibility and devotion in society based on this heritage, have been examined in the scientific works of scholars such as James R. Ozinga, Jacob Neusner, George Herbert Palmer, Robin Gill, Andrew Michael Fletcher, V. N. Podshivalov, G. V. Lakazova, A. Frolov, V. Kinelev, I. Kosova, B. Azarov, L. Vygotsky, S. Rubinstein, V. Bepalko, E. Yusupov, S. Otamurodov, I. Saifnazarov, M. Imomnazarov, M. Nurmatova, I. Khojamurodov, U. Uvatov, U. Kushayev, and I. Ergashev.

Results and discussion

In the era of globalization, the global situation is changing rapidly, and in some regions of the world, conditions are becoming increasingly tense. Contradictions, conflicts, and bloodshed are intensifying, while the threats of international terrorism and extremism are growing. Such circumstances are causing deep concern and anxiety across the world. Some researchers emphasize that addressing these threats largely falls on Uzbekistan, as it plays a key role in the region and faces the challenges of international terrorism, drug trafficking, and external aggression.

In such a complex and unpredictable situation, people must maintain a high level of vigilance, constant readiness, and—most importantly—responsibility and devotion. This process begins with an understanding of cultural values and comprehension of spiritual heritage. A nation that knows and appreciates its history, culture, and spirituality, and draws moral strength from them, cannot be defeated by any external force—this truth has become even clearer today.

The reconstruction of the authentic history of the Uzbek people began with the formation of a unified concept for studying its millennia-old heritage. This process, which has become a continuous and responsible task, has strengthened the historical and methodological foundations for interpreting the ideas of responsibility and devotion. Simultaneously, it has reinforced a national mentality-based system for nurturing these qualities among the youth.

Therefore, the analysis of historical sources and the resulting scientific-theoretical conclusions, generalizations, and lessons allow for a more objective understanding of the principle of education in the spirit of responsibility and devotion. Moreover, these findings can contribute to shaping the activities of government institutions in implementing the paradigm of devotion.

The conceptual foundations of education in the spirit of responsibility and devotion can be applied in developing modern paradigms of loyalty and commitment, which play a crucial role in shaping the devoted individual of the 21st-century Uzbek society.

It is particularly important to note that the spiritual foundation of the Uzbek people, which serves as the pillar of our statehood, is both ancient and robust. This cultural and spiritual heritage harmoniously combines three essential aspects:

1. Secular enlightenment;
2. Religious-philosophical thought;
3. Spiritual-moral ideals.

The third aspect, in particular, has served as a key moral foundation in helping the Uzbek people regain their identity and restore their national pride after independence. In this regard, studying and analyzing examples of responsibility and devotion within the spiritual and moral heritage of the Uzbek people through the criteria of moral courage is especially relevant and meaningful.

The concept of “**spiritual courage**” (**ma’naviy jasorat**) was introduced into scientific discourse by the **First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov**, who recognized spiritual courage as *the highest form of bravery*. He stated:

“All immortal monuments on earth, all the great discoveries and inventions that have radically changed human life, the masterpieces of classical art and literature, and the

examples of bravery and heroism are the result of humanity's intellect, potential, and spiritual courage."

The heroism of our ancestors—who embodied the **measure, demand, and essence of spiritual courage** as *examples of bravery and heroism that reflect universal human values*—holds universal significance.

Based on the above definition, the **criteria, requirements, and characteristics** of spiritual courage can be defined as follows:

- events and phenomena that have radically transformed human life;
- examples of bravery and heroism embodying universal human values;
- manifestations that emerged as the product of intellect and reasoning;
- virtuous actions that reflect the realization of human potential.

Conclusion

In the current era, it is essential to study the manifestations of **responsibility** and **devotion** within the spiritual and moral heritage of the Uzbek people from a **historical perspective**, and to critically reassess the experiences of our ancestors through the analysis of reliable archival sources.

A well-developed scientific study in this field will not only enrich scholarship with previously unknown historical and social materials and documents but also help clarify the essence of the issues in new methodological approaches to the study of national history. Moreover, it will serve as a foundation for determining the directions of comprehensive future research.

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